

A Review of Synthesis and Biological Activities of 1,3,4-Oxadiazole Derivatives

Vinny Varghese¹, Silvipriya K S², Meena Chandran^{3*}, Aleena Rose Johnson⁴, Anusha N D⁵, K Krishna Kumar⁶

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, St James' College of Pharmaceutical Sciences and St. James' Hospital Trust
Pharmaceutical Research (DSIR) Chalakudy, Kerala, India. Pin code - 680307

Abstract

One important type of heterocyclic compound is 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles, which are molecules with one oxygen atom and two nitrogen atoms organised in a five-membered ring. It has been demonstrated that 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives have a wide range of uses, from industrial development as corrosion inhibitors and light-emitting diodes to medicinal chemistry for the treatment and potential treatment of numerous illnesses. Such structures are crucial to contemporary agriculture and have been effectively employed in the treatment of a number of human and animal illnesses. Numerous oxadiazole compounds have been shown to display antifungal, blood pressure-lowering, antibacterial, antiviral, antineoplastic, anticancer, and antioxidant analgesic and anti-inflammatory qualities. Furthermore, substances derived from 1,3,4-oxadiazole can possess herbicidal, insecticidal, and fungicidal properties that make them effective plant protection agents. Because of the ongoing interest in such heterocyclic systems, novel techniques for acquiring complex structures with rings of oxadiazole are desired. Numerous feasible synthetic pathways that produced 1,3,4-oxadiazoles in extremely high yields utilizing environmentally friendly methods may be the cause of these various life-altering applications. This review explores several techniques for production of biologically active 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives. Using these methods, the formed derivatives may find application in agriculture and medicine in the future.

Keywords: Heterocyclic compound, 1,3,4-Oxadiazole, Anticancer, Herbicidal.

INTRODUCTION

A significant class of heterocyclic compounds with two nitrogen atoms and one oxygen atom arranged in a five-membered ring are the 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles. It is produced from furan by substituting two nitrogen (-N=) of the pyridine type for two methylene groups (=CH). 1,3,4-Oxadiazole derivatives have been demonstrated to have antifungal, blood pressure-lowering, antiviral, antibacterial, antineoplastic, anticancer, antioxidant, analgesic, and anti-inflammatory properties. It is an essential building unit in several drugs including the broad-spectrum antibacterial drug furamizole^[1], the antiretroviral drug raltegravir^[2], the anticancer agent zibotentan.^[3] There is a growing interest in the chemotherapeutic activities of 2,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles as antibacterial^{[4],[5]}, antifungal^{[6],[7]}, antitubercular^{[8],[9]} and antiviral agents.^{[10],[11]}

1,3,4-Oxadiazole

Fig. 1: Structure of 1,3,4-Oxadiazole

When creating 1,3,4-oxadiazoles, the most popular synthesis pathway involves direct interactions between acid hydrazides (or hydrazine) and acid chlorides or carboxylic acids. Diacylhydrazine cyclisation employing a range of dehydrating substances like thionyl chloride and phosphorous oxychloride^{[12],[13]}, triflic anhydride^[14], phosphorous pentoxide^[15], The direct interaction of the acid with (N-isocyanimino-) and polyphosphoric acid^[16], tetramethylphosphorane.^{[17]–[20]}

Fig. 2: Structure of 1,3,4-Oxadiazole containing drugs

Different Methods Used to Synthesis 1,3,4-Oxadiazole derivatives

Synthesis of new series of Schiff base-type hybrid compounds containing 1,3,4-oxadiazole ring ^[21]

In ethanol media, hydrazide **1**, KOH and carbon disulphide combine to form 4,6-Dimethyl-*N*-[(5-sulfanylidene-4,5-dihydro-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)methyl]-2-sulfanylpiperidine-3-carboxamide **2**. It was then react with potassium hydroxide, ethanol, water and ethyl bromoacetate to produce Ethyl 2-(5-((2-sulfanyl-4,6-dimethylpyridine-3-carboxamido)methyl)-2-sulfanylidene-2,3-dihydro-1,3,4-oxadiazol-3-yl)acetate **3**. Methanolic solution of **3** is refluxed with hydrazine hydrate to form *N*-{[4-(2-hydrazinyl-2-oxoethyl)-5-sulfanylidene-4,5-dihydro-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]methyl}-4,6-dimethyl-2-sulfanylpiperidine-3-carboxamide **4**. Further it reacted with acetic acid and appropriate benzaldehyde in methanolic media, various 1,3,4-Oxadiazole Derivatives of 4,6-Dimethyl-2-sulfanylpiperidine-3-carboxamide (**5-13**) were formed.

Fig. 3: Synthesis of new series of Schiff base-type hybrid compounds containing 1,3,4-oxadiazole ring

Table 1: 1,3,4-Oxadiazole Derivatives of 4,6-Dimethyl-2-sulfanylpuridine-3-carboxamide

Compound	R
5	H
6	4-F
7	4-CH ₃
8	4-SCH ₂
9	4-CN
10	4-Cl
11	4-CF ₂
12	3-Cl
13	2-Br

Synthesis of 1,3,4-Oxadiazole N-Mannich Bases ^[22]

The methyl 3,4-dimethoxybenzoate was treated with hydrazine in ethanol to yield the 3,4-Dimethoxybenzohydrazide. By reacting the carbohydrazide with carbon disulphide in ethanolic potassium hydroxide, 1,3,4-Oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione was produced. Additionally, it has been observed that 1,3,4-Oxadiazole-2(3H)-thiones undergo aminomethylation by reacting with formaldehyde and primary aromatic amines to produce the appropriate N-Mannich bases. The corresponding 3-arylaminoethyl or 3-piperazinomethyl N-Mannich bases were thus produced in good yields by treating 1,3,4-Oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione with formaldehyde solution and different primary aromatic amines or 1-substituted piperazines in ethanol at room temperature.

Fig. 4: Synthesis of 1,3,4-Oxadiazole N-Mannich Bases

Table 2: 1,3,4-Oxadiazole N-Mannich Bases

Compound	X	Compound	X	Compound	R
4a	H	4g	4-NO ₂		
4b	4-F	4h	2-CF ₃	5a	C ₆ H ₅
4c	3-Cl	4i	3-CF ₃	5b	4-FC ₆ H ₄
4d	4-Cl	4j	2,4-F ₂	5c	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂
4e	2-NO ₂	4k	2,5 -F ₂	5d	2-CF ₃ C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂
4f	3-NO ₂	4l	2,4-Cl ₂		

Synthesis of *N'*-(1-(2-(3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-3(2*H*)-yl)-ethylidene) substituted hydrazides ^[23]

The chalcone derivative, *N'*-(3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazole-4-carbaldehyde)benzohydrazide (**2**), was prepared by refluxing 3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazole-4-carbaldehyde (**1**) with benzohydrazide in 1,4-dioxane. The intermediate 1-(2-(3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-3(2*H*)-yl)ethenone (**3**) is produced by refluxing the chalcone derivative (**2**) in acetic anhydride. A well-dissolved mixture of intermediate (**3**), appropriate benzohydrazides, and a pinch of anhydrous ZnCl₂ in ethanol is refluxed to yield *N'*-(1-(2-(3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-3(2*H*)-yl)ethylidene) substituted hydrazides (**4a-t**).

Fig. 5: Synthesis of *N'*-(1-(2-(3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-3(2*H*)-yl)-ethylidene)substituted hydrazides

Table 3: N'-(1-(2-(3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-3(2H)-yl)-ethylidene)substituted hydrazides

Compound	R	Compound	R
4a	-C ₆ H ₅	4k	-CH ₂ - C ₆ H ₅
4b	-2-OH- C ₆ H ₄	4l	-CH ₂ NHCO- C ₆ H ₅
4c	-3-OH- C ₆ H ₄	4m	-CH ₂ -O- C ₆ H ₄ -2-CH ₃
4d	-4-OH- C ₆ H ₄	4n	-CH ₂ -O- C ₆ H ₄ -3-CH ₃
4e	-4-NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	4o	-CH ₂ -O- C ₆ H ₄ -4-CH ₃
4f	-3-CH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	4p	-CH ₂ -O- C ₆ H ₄ -2-NO ₂
4g	-4-CH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	4q	-CH ₂ -O- C ₆ H ₄ -3-NO ₂
4h	-4-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	4r	-CH ₂ -O- C ₆ H ₄ -4-NO ₂
4i	-3-Cl- C ₆ H ₄	4s	-CH ₂ -O- C ₆ H ₄ -2-Cl
4j	-4-Cl- C ₆ H ₄	4t	-CH ₂ -O- C ₆ H ₄ -4-Cl

Synthesis of 2,5-substituted Diphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole ^[24]

The synthesis of substituted diphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole involved cyclisation by the addition of phosphorus oxychloride after ester substitution of substituted benzohydrazide in the presence of hydrazine hydrate.

Fig. 6: Synthesis of 2,5-substituted Diphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole

Table 4: 2,5-substituted Diphenyl-1,3,4-

Compound	R	R ¹
XIII	4-OH	4-Cl
XIV	4-NO ₂	4-Cl
XV	4-NO ₂	4-NO ₂
XVI	4-NO ₂	4-NH ₂
XVII	4-OH	4-NH ₂
XVIII	4-NO ₂	2-Br
XIX	4-NH ₂	4-Cl
XX	4-NO ₂	4-OH
XXI	4-OH	2-Br
XXII	4-NO ₂	H

oxadiazole

Synthesis of 1-(4-Methoxy-phenyl)-3-[5-(substituted phenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]propan-1-one ^[25]

Fischer esterification was used to create ethyl esters from substituted aromatic acids, which then reacted with hydrazine hydrate in the presence of ethanol to produce the appropriate hydrazide derivative. In the presence of phosphorus oxychloride (a cyclodehydrating agent), the hydrazide derivatives then interacted with β-benzoyl propionic acid to produce the final products.

Fig. 7: Synthesis of 1-(4-Methoxy-phenyl)-3-[5-(substituted phenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]propan-1-one

Table 5: 1-(4-Methoxy-phenyl)-3-[5-(substituted phenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]propan-1-one

Compound	R
6a	-C ₆ H ₅
6b	-4-NH ₂ C ₆ H ₄
6c	-4-OH- C ₆ H ₄
6d	-2-OH- C ₆ H ₄
6e	-4-Cl- C ₆ H ₄
6f	-2-Cl- C ₆ H ₄
6g	-4-CH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄
6h	-4-NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄

Biological Activities of 1,3,4-Oxadiazole Derivatives

Central Nervous System depressant activity ^[24]

Singh *et al.*, (2012) had created and assessed derivatives of substituted diphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole for their ability to depress the central nervous system. The synthesis involved cyclisation by the addition of phosphorus oxychloride after ester substitution of substituted benzohydrazide in the presence of hydrazine hydrate. Among the synthesized compounds, those with electron withdrawing substituents: 5-(4-Nitrophenyl)-2-(4-chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole and 5-(4-Nitrophenyl)-2-(4-nitrophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole showed excellent antidepressant activity.

2-(4-Chlorophenyl)-5-(4-nitrophenyl)
-1,3,4-oxadiazole

2-(4-Nitrophenyl)-5-(4-nitrophenyl)
-1,3,4-oxadiazole

Fig. 8: Central Nervous System depressant activity of 2,5-substituted Diphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole

Antioxidant activity ^[26]

SM Rana *et al.*, (2023) created 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives by adding the flurbiprofen moiety in an effort to investigate target compounds' ability to reduce oxidative stress. In order to create the targeted compounds, a flurbiprofen-COOH group was esterified with methanol in an acid-catalyzed medium. This was followed by a reaction with hydrazine to produce the appropriate hydrazide. After reacting with CS₂ in the presence of KOH, the acid hydrazide was cyclized into 1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiol. The targeted derivatives were synthesized by the reaction of an -SH group with various alkyl/aryl chlorides, which involves an S-alkylation reaction. By assessing the produced compounds' ability to

scavenge free radicals, such as DPPH, OH, nitric oxide (NO), and iron chelation assay, their overall antioxidant capacity has been assessed. At 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, the derivative 2-(5-[1-(2-Fluorobiphenyl-4-yl)ethyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)sulfanyl)-N-(4-chlorophenyl)acetamide shown a good 80.23% radical scavenging potential, while ascorbic acid showed 87.72% inhibition at the same dose.

Fig. 9: Structure of 2-(5-[1-(2-Fluorobiphenyl-4-yl) ethyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl) sulfanyl)-N-(4-chlorophenyl)acetamide

Anti-inflammatory activity ^[21]

Świątek P *et al.*, (2022) In addition to corticosteroids, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medications (NSAIDs) are used to treat inflammatory symptoms, especially in chronic conditions. But still their usage is restricted due to their toxicity from COX inhibition and the suppression of prostaglandins that are physiologically significant. Following the review, a new set of Schiff base-type hybrid with a 1,3,4-oxadiazole ring, 4,6-dimethylpyridine core, and N-acyl hydrazone components that are substituted differently are designed, synthesised, and anti-COX-1/COX-2 activity were evaluated. The compound 4,6-Dimethyl-N-{[4-(2-(2-(2-bromobenzylidene) hydrazinyl)-2-oxoethyl)-5-sulfanylidene-4,5-dihydro-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl] methyl}-2-sulfanylpyridine-3-carboxamide inhibited the activity of both isoenzymes, COX-1 and COX-2 at a lower concentration than standard drug, Meloxicam.

Fig. 10: Structure of 4,6-Dimethyl-N-{[4-(2-(2-(2-bromobenzylidene) hydrazinyl)-2-oxoethyl)-5-sulfanylidene-4,5-dihydro-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl] methyl}-2-sulfanylpyridine-3-carboxamide

Anti-cancer activity ^[27]

ASA Almalki *et al.*, (2021) Thymol-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives containing 1,2,3-triazole have been synthesised and their anticancer property is evaluated. Of these active derivatives, compound 2-(4-((5-((2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenoxy) methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-ylthio) methyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazol-1-yl) Phenol was the most effective chemical against the three cell lines that were tested: HepG2 (IC₅₀ 1.4 μM), HCT-116 (IC₅₀ 2.6 μM), and MCF-7 (IC₅₀ 1.1 μM). It was determined to be superior to 5-fluorouracil and doxorubicin, the conventional medications. Through thymidylate synthase inhibition, these drugs demonstrated anticancer action. Their IC₅₀ ranged from 1.95 to 4.24 μM , indicating considerable TS inhibitory activity, while the reference medication, Pemetrexed, had an IC₅₀ of 7.26 μM .

Fig. 11: Structure of 2-(4-((5-((2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenoxy) methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-ylthio) methyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazol-1-yl)Phenol

Antimicrobial activity ^[27]

ASA Almalki et al., (2021) The antibacterial properties of thymol-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives comprising 1,2,3-triazole have been synthesised and assessed. According to the antibacterial findings, the substances 4-((5-((2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenoxy)methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-ylthio)methyl)-1-phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazole and 2-(4-((5-((2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenoxy)methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-ylthio)methyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazol-1-yl)Phenol showed effective suppression of *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) and *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*).

4-((5-((2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenoxy) methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-ylthio) methyl)-1-phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazole

2-(4-((5-((2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenoxy) methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-ylthio) methyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazol-1-yl)Phenol

Fig. 12: Structure of compounds showing antimicrobial activity

Conclusion

Substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles are of considerable pharmaceutical interest by the virtue of -N = C-O- grouping. A number of biological actions, including CNS depressive, anti-cancer, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties, are exhibited by 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles. As a result, they present a viable platform for the creation of numerous innovative medications. In summary, the synthetic methods used to create 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles and their biological activity are detailed.

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